

Polihierax semitorquatus Pygmy falcon

Decoding
South Africa's
Biodiversity

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Group: Bird

Size: 20 cm (length)

Distribution:

Two disjunct populations occur. The subspecies *Polihierax semitorquatus semitorquatus* (sequenced here) occurs from Angola to northern South Africa, while *P. s. castanonotus* is found from South Sudan to Somalia and south to Tanzania.

Importance:

The pygmy falcon is important to South African biodiversity, helping control insect and small vertebrate populations in arid environments. It exhibits cooperative breeding, where non-breeding individuals assist in raising chicks, which may enhance breeding success. Finally, the pygmy falcon does not build its own nest but instead breeds in the large communal nests of the sociable weaver in South Africa. This a fascinating example of a commensal relationship, with some mutualistic benefits.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 78.63 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 5.48 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Genome Length: 1.22 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 99.6% [Single: 98.4%, Duplicated: 1.2%]

Assembly N50: 2 723.9 kilobases

Contig number: 3 739

Sample Contributor contact details:

Prof. Robert Ingle

University of Cape Town

robert.ingle@uct.ac.za

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Date Published: 2025-07-17
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.16355799